

YOSEMITE NATURE NOTES

DEPARTMENT *of the* INTERIOR
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that the 1928 crop proved to be all females is particularly fortunate, for until then the herd had ten bulls and only six cows. Now the number is almost evenly divided between the sexes. It is to be

hoped that females will preponderate greatly among the calves dropped next May, for the herd would be more nearly ideal if there were twice as many or more cows than bulls.

RING-TAILED CATS AT GLACIER POINT

By J. B. Herschler

We usually think of ring-tailed cats (*Bassariscus astutus raptor*) as belonging to the foothills region or Upper Sonoran zone, but it has been my good fortune to observe them at Glacier Point, an elevation in Yosemite of 7200 feet.

While assigned there as ranger naturalist, employes at the cafeteria told me of seeing them occasionally and it was my desire to see them also, but when my assignment was completed, ring-tailed cats remained more of a myth and a mystery than a reality, for not a single one had shown itself while I was there.

While preparing to return to the floor of the valley a way became apparent that observations might be made. The night watchman was leaving and I could have his place if I cared to. Willingly it was accepted as the work took only a part of the time leaving the balance free for nature study.

The first appearance of cats came one evening about 7 o'clock. They had been seen in the woodshed but by the time I arrived they had gone. While making the midnight round several nights later I did see two of them near the roof on top of the wood which was piled there. They were far enough away to feel secure and did not object to the ray from the flashlight being thrown upon them and were not at all frightened.

They appeared inquisitive but after a few minutes they disappeared. Some nights later the pantry door had not been fastened securely and shortly after midnight I was attracted by a noise inside and upon entering found that two ring-tails were the originators. When the light was turned on, one took refuge behind some food cases while the other perched on a beam overhead. Evidently the latter had taken a piece of meat along for it soon began chewing and eating as though no one were near. It was perhaps only four or five feet above my head but was not uneasy when I walked under. The other one, not feeling so secure, made several frantic trips around the pantry and finally crawled behind a screened food container where it was pretty well cornered. Having a clear view of it through the screen I reached around behind and stroked it on the tail, which made it very nervous, but even with this discomfort it did not try to escape. Instead it started making a sort of chuckling, hissing noise accompanied by a slight, rapid up and down movement of the head.

One morning later while making the 1 o'clock round I heard a thud on the veranda and hurriedly turning on the flashlight saw one go down over the edge. Upon looking to see where it had jumped from when I heard the noise, I found a

window open in an unoccupied room. Curious to know what it was doing I went inside and found a second one still there. Closing the window so it could not escape I tried to make friends with it but it hid behind the radiator and would not be driven out until I put a cord around its neck. By pulling on the cord and pushing with a stick it was dislodged. After some minutes of frantically trying to get away it became quiet and sullen. And not until after about an hour of handling and petting did the beautiful little creature seem to realize that no harm was intended and it began to be more friendly. Finally I perched it on one arm and held out a piece of beefsteak. It made a fierce grab as though to

commit murder but when it got the taste quieted down immediately and began to eat, not stopping until the whole piece had been finished.

In order to get pictures I placed the animal in a large wooden bucket until morning, when I got a series of seven passable photographs that I prize highly.

Always I was on the lookout for cats and did see them several times more but it would usually be from 11 p. m. to 2 a. m. The earliest in the evening I saw them was about 7 o'clock and the latest in the morning was about 4 and never in the daytime. Having never seen more than two at a time I concluded it was a single pair that had ventured so far up the mountain and had decided to make a home under man's protection.

THE BAND-TAILED PIGEON'S NEST

By Enid Michael

On August 3, 1928, a pair of band-tailed pigeons (*Columba fasciata*) was discovered at work on a nest. The nest was placed on a horizontal branch of an incense cedar. It was some 20 feet above the ground and but a few inches from the main stem of the tree. As is the usual case when we find the nest of a pigeon, our attention was first attracted by the sound of snapping twigs. The band-tailed pigeon gathers no nesting material from the ground. The male bird flies into a tree, usually a living cedar here in the valley, takes a perch, and gazes about in search of a suitable twig. While making up his mind as to just which twig he really wants, he has a strange way of bobbing his head. He draws his head back deliberately and then jabs it forward with a quick, jerky

movement. When he decides on the dead twig he wants, he flies to the branch, walks slowly out along the limb, leans over, grasps the twig firmly in his mandibles, and with a quick twist of his head the twig is snapped off. Now with a great clatter of wings he flies to the nest-tree. If the limb containing the nest-site is limber, he does not alight directly upon it but comes to perch above or below and approaches the nest by a series of "flight hops." While the male is out foraging for nesting material, the female waits more or less patiently at the nest-site. She receives the material from her mate and does the actual work of construction. And between the two, if the truth must be known, the nest is no work of art.

By climbing a Douglas spruce